

**THE MOTIF OF THE DEATH IN KHOSIYAT RUSTAMOVA'S
POETRY.**

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Abstract: Not only is new literature a new word, but it also represents a new pain, way of thinking, and height. One of the primary research topics of philosophical lyrics of today, as of all times, is the dilemma of time and human. One form of creative expression that initially connects with any social events is lyric poetry.

This article discusses the poetry of Khosiyat Rustamova, a well-known artist who has a special place in modern Uzbek poetry. The poet's works will be studied in depth, and her style of using words, her ability to utilize themes and motifs will be analyzed. Expression of the motif of death in the works of the poetess is based on specific rhymes. Besides, in this article, theoretical analyzes are presented regarding the use of the motif of death in her works of poetry.

Key words: poetry, style, form, theme, motif, image, a lyrical hero, life, death, landscape image, psyche, spirit.

Along with the fact that modern Uzbek poetry is increasingly rich in formal and methodological research, it also shows a deeper understanding that literature is inextricably linked with the human heart. It is considered a positive phenomenon that a person's psyche and life actions are widely depicted in literature, especially in poetry. It is gratifying to see that the number of artists who are writing poems in the field of poetry is increasing and incorporating these features into their works.

Khosiyat Rustamova, the talented daughter of Namangan, is one of the representatives of modern poetry, which recently entered the Uzbek literature. Khosiyat Rustamova entered the field of creativity after such poets as Zebo Mirzo and Halima Ahmad, but with her unique poems, she managed to win the hearts of many

poetry lovers. Her poems were translated into other languages of the world and found foreign fans.

Khosiyat Rustamova was born in Chust, Namangan, whose description in Uzbekistan has spread to the world. She graduated from the Faculty of Journalism of the National University of Uzbekistan. "House in the Sky" (1997), "Salvation" (2003), "Wall" (2006), "August" (2008), "Occupation" (2011), "40:0" (2011) and a number of other books by the poetess were published.

The themes of her poems are diverse, including love, Motherland, nature and as well as many philosophical poems. It should be emphasized that the analysis of her poems requires great observation and skill. The reason that is, not only modern poetry is just about reading, but also it invites readers to try to realize the meaning.

Khosiyat Rustamova is one of the people who managed to express her words and thoughts based on new principles from her first steps into the world of artistic creation. We can see this in the example of the analysis of the lines written by the poetess:

“Nima bo‘lsa – bo‘ladi tamom,
Go‘zal hislar uyg‘otdi mani.
Ketayapman ohanglar tomon –
Sening bilan xayrlashgani”.

In the lines quoted above, the poet appears in the form of a lyrical hero who surrenders to his fate, wakes up from the shock of beautiful feelings and sets out to say goodbye to his beloved following the beautiful melodies. The fact that the verses are stated in a simple and consistent manner, the simplicity and the purity of the artistic expression are evident, ensure the legibility of this poem.

Khosiyat Rustamova is a poetess of deep thought and high taste. In her poetry, along with the tones of feeling the joy of real life, optimistic spirit, partial pain, sad mood, and natural compassion also play a significant role.

Indeed, she does not simply write any verse. In her writings, you can see anxiety about the fate of others along with her own destiny, and in the true sense, she feels sympathy for people. This quality, so to speak, is one of the first necessary qualities

for poets. Therefore, her writings do not leave anyone indifferent, they are always appreciated and always adored by readers.

Yo'q, bunaqa bo'lmaydi yashash,
Nahot, shunday yashayman toki...
Men jonimni xudodan emas,
Birovlardan oldim go'yoki...
Yo'q bunaqa bo'lmaydi yashash.
Har bir daraxt,
Har bitta giyoh
Buncha yuvosh, buncha boadab!
Aytganini qiladi Dunyo —
O'tirmaydi ko'nglingga qarab.
Yo'q, bunaqa bo'lmaydi yashash.
O'zni qo'lga olasan arang,
Ich-ichingga cho'kadi faryod.
Bir ozgina ko'proq yashasang —
Ta'na qila boshlaydi Hayot.
Yo'q, bunaqa bo'lmaydi yashash...

These lines are so unique! In the above stanzas, there is a whole world of meaning. As we read these verses, we support each word of her in the lines and want to rebel against this transitory life.

Khosiyat Rustamova's poetry is full of various themes such as homeland and freedom, war and peace, life and death, nature and human, charity and love. Although she has written poems regarding traditional themes, her writing and expressing style surprise readers. Ideas and motifs in her works attract all people, as a result, they become fascinated by author's poems.

Speaking of motifs, I would like to note that what stands out as a motif in most of her works is the symbol of death. The death represented many things for author, which in turn reflects its importance to her. As such, there are various motifs of the death in

her poetry, whose meanings would shift from time to time as her life goes on. The following poem entitled “Death” skillfully expresses the author's attitude towards death.

Har gal Seni eslaganda
Titrar vujud,
Tomirlarda jimirlaydi
Qon tomchisi.
Hayot haqda gapirmas hech
Ishontirib,
Bu dunyoning Sendan boshqa yolg'onchisi.

Death has always been a traditional theme for poetry and therefore it is not surprising that it was important to Khosiyat Rustamova too. A lot of poems, dealing with death, are proof enough for her enormous interest in this theme. When we read the poems, we can witness that in Hosiyyat Rustamova's poems, death is not only a theme, but also a motif as mentioned above.

To be specific, we will explore the motif of death, how it developed and evolved over time and try to find out what inspired her to create these works of poetry in the first place. The poems in analysis are “Bugun bog'lar qora kiyimda”, “Sal narsaga to'kasan ko'z yosh”, “Xazon”, “O'lim”, “Egishe Charens”.

Bugun bog'lar qora kiyimda —
Maysalarni qopladi zahar.
Yuzin to'sib mening uyimda —
Uvvos solib yig'ladi shahar.
Gumburladi nimadir ko'kda,
Changalladi ko'ksin allakim.
Qora xalqqa otilgan o'qdan
Yaralandi mening yuragim.

The word of death is not directly given in this poem, but we can see that the author shows the funeral with her descriptive expressions such as “gardens in black” (bog'lar

qora kiyimda), “the city cried loudly” (uvvos solib yig’ladi shahar), “a bullet fired at black (common) people” (qora xalqqa otilgan o’q). She draws the image of death in order to demonstrate her reflections on social injustice for common people.

Sal narsaga to’kasan ko’zyosh,
Ne ko’ylarga solasan mani.
O, yuragim, berasanmi dosh —
Taqdirimda o’lmoq bor hali.

This poem is not about death, but the poet acknowledges that death is a fact of life through her reference to the image of the heart in the verses and emphasizes that she obeys the general laws of nature.

Gul bilan xazonni barobar etding,
Ketar chog’ — baxtiyor ketding havolab.
Meni o’lim bilan birodar etding,
O, meni ko’nglimni qo’yding jazolab.
Ortingdan boraman —
Ko’rsat yo’lingni,
Ko’rsat — shox-shabbalar ichidan yurib.
Dunyo tortmay qo’ydi
E’tiborimni,
Dunyo xazon kabi qoldi uyulib.

This poem was entitled by author as “Xazon” (falling leaves). This poem describes the process of falling leaves in autumn. Describing the fall of autumn leaves, the poet compares this process to the end of a lifetime. In the last stanzas, the poetess writes about how she was forced to make friends with death as her life was coming to an end.

Yaxshilarning tushar izidan,
Yomonlarni suymaydi jini.
Bu dunyoda hatto o’lim ham
Yerga urmas ekan qadrini.

The next poem "Death" was written in memory of Abdusalam Madrahimov. Through this poem, she says that the value of death is high, and she explains it by the fact that it follows good people only. In addition, this poem shows the author's loss of a close person and expresses separation.

To'rt tomoniga "Non" deb yozilgan
Qora mashinalar o'tsa yonimdan —
Mening vujudimni qoplaydi titroq...
Qarayman... Odamlar ko'zida quvonch,
Cho'ntakda bor nonga yetadigan pul.
Menda mashinaga yo'q ishonch.
Balki unda yo'qdir yangi pishgan non,
Nega bu odamlar boqar behadik.
Balki endigina uzilgan o'lik...
Katta harflarda "Non" deb yozilgan
Qora mashinalar o'tsa yonimdan —
"Egishe Charens" deb hayqirgim kelar...

"In 1937, on one of the streets of Yerevan, a huge car with the inscription "Bread" on its side, carried the body of the great Armenian poet Egishe Charens, hiding it from the eyes of the people and burying it." This inscription was chosen as an epigraph to the above poem. This poem written by the poetess is a manifesto against oppression and injustice in society on behalf of humanity.

As you have witnessed, motif of death in Khosiyat Rustamova's poems symbolizes her reflections on social injustice for common people, obedience to the general laws of nature, separation, loneliness, memory and a great manifesto against oppression and injustice in society.

To sum up, as stated in the above-mentioned opinions, first of all, works of poetry should calm the human psyche, lead it to goodness, or, in simple words, change it for the better. Only then will it fulfill its true spiritual duty. It is no exaggeration to say that the features of the original artistic work are clearly reflected in the poetry of the poetess

Khosiyat Rustamova, whose works we have analyzed. The charm of sincere and simple language, the burning tones of a painful and dreamy heart in her poems are the proof of our opinion.

Khosiyat Rustamova's poetry is an expression of unique landscapes, beautiful themes and magical images. Her works are examples of real artistic creations, saturated with feelings and thoughts, decorated with deep aesthetic taste, which can reveal the lines of the human psyche.

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